

Investigating the Status of Risk Management System in Tunnel Construction Projects

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Abstract

Tunnel projects considered as one of the complex and dangerous infrastructure projects due to the attribute of such projects as it progressively achieves highly risk and uncertainties during project implementation. Such kind of projects is highly expected that a real and dependable system of risk management to be implemented throughout the project phases to ensure the completion in a best way possible. Unfortunately, in reality, it is away far from expectation for the projects of tunnel implemented here in Iraq because no reasonable system of risk implemented just only a construction management system that depends only on the experience of the project staff and some expert senior engineers with no availability of a dependent system of risk control and management. The paper will provide investigation regarding reality of risk system in tunnel projects with the aid of questionnaires and provide such fact that there is a low limited knowledge of risk management concept. Using principle of like hood and impact concepts risk matrix conducted. Forty-four risk factors presented through the study and prioritize depending on their risk degree, accordingly top ten risk factors presented. Throughout the results by means of data collected during the survey, it was clear that the results were heading to such a fact that risk management is not implemented; and applied in such projects. Results regarding risk management concepts were in range (66.67 up to 100%) were with negative answers. this led to the fact that the need for risk management understanding and implementing is a crucial quest with the intention to obtain tunnel project objectives considering (time, cost, quality & safety) to avoid time and cost overruns and any other obstacles.

Keywords: Tunnel, Risk, Risk Management, Uncertainty, Project Objectives, Reality

1. Introduction

For infrastructure projects such as tunnels, main road, bridges and so on the process of risk management is in need to avoid any catastrophe that will lead to stop, long time delay, massive cost

overrun and accidents. Tunnel projects, regardless of the reason of construction; road tunnel, drainage corridor or utility tunnel. Such a project with a great concern should handle in such way that a dependable systematic way of management to apply in which it includes the principal way of

managing the phases of the tunnel project. Such projects always face risks and uncertainties during different phases of the project, starting from the pre-study to the operation and control of the tunnel. According to [5] risk management is “The organized systematic process of identifying, analyzing and eventually responding to project risks”. In any way for project risk management definitions used, the overall purpose of such risk management mostly remains the same, which is definitely to take in information and approaches from the different phases of the project on a specific aspect of uncertainty. In this way, that procedure is required to consider the past issues prompting inconveniences, present difficulties and prevalent tendencies that approach the task's effective execution. Risk management[4] considered valuable part of any project management system and is in a tunnel project in special has a major role to attain the project objectives “time, cost, quality & safety” therefore; there should be a systematic risk management and analysis for such projects in order to avoid time and cost overruns. Unfortunately, through the paper it was found that no systematic approaches applied nor implemented during the projects only depending on the experience of the project managers and senior engineers and some other parties that has experience in that field of construction to solve the matters related to risks affecting the project as a whole.

2. Risk management in tunnel projects Body

The risk is a basal natural element of life and defined as “the possibility of something happening that will have an influence on objectives” [1]. A conventional definition of risk degree (R); is that risk is proportional to a measure for the probability (P) of an event (frequency, likelihood) and the consequences (C) of an event (impact, effect on objectives) as in (1):

$$R = (P * C) \dots (1)$$

The scale of risk should be measured by both the likelihood of an event occurring and the severity of impact if it were to happen[2],[3]. The risk matrix thereafter can used as a risk register for ongoing tracking and overview of risk during the life of a project. Risk factors are the ones highlighted in which they affect the project objectives such as time, cost, quality & safety. The objective of risk management, in general, is to manage every issue can described as dangerous to project accomplishment undertaking and its specific circumstance. This executed by sorting out those issues based on the recurrence of the event, level of

effect, significance pursued by the plans expected to control the recognized dangers. Tunnels built in different geotechnical conditions, which can be described as unknown and uncertain environment ahead of tunnel construction. Other factors influencing the project success come from the human and organizational factors, therefore, project parties urged to use a systematic relabel risk management plans. Tunneling projects consist of multiple events and complicated technical systems. Therefore, risk management is with great concern in such projects.

Throughout the paper, different factors and questions mentioned describing the base of knowledge to risk management, risk management concept, risk management, risk factors, and eventually the reality of such system of risk in tunnel projects in Kurdistan region-Iraq.

3. Preliminary Study

For the study, a qualitative risk analysis applied by conducting a form of opened and closed questionnaires. Including questions regarding risk management significance and whether it is clear or no, a list of risk factors and another list to show the risk responsibilities of project members for some itemed risks at different construction phases that may occur during the project. The questionnaires were delivered to respondents related to the field of tunnel construction only including five major tunnel projects within 30 eligible respondents were accepted and analyzed.

4. Objectives and Significant

the main objective intent for this paper is to try and identify the risk factors in such projects (tunnels); and so on to prioritize those factors accordingly; by expedient of questionnaires; and so as analyze, as well as to show the reality of do the staff of project have the required information and knowledge regarding risk or no. In addition, as significant to show that how much risk management applied in such projects here in Iraq.

5. Methodology and Procedure

As been planned for such study methodologies adopted within were as follows:

- ❖ Selecting area of study (tunnel projects) with site visits to the area.
- ❖ Preparation of questionnaires.
- ❖ Questionnaire survey and with direct interviews with related parties within the tunnel projects
- ❖ Analyzing the questionnaires.
- ❖ Show through the answers how much the knowledge for staff is regarding risk.

- ❖ Whether risk management is applied, as it should be or no.
- ❖ Detecting the factors of risk that affect the tunnel project and prioritize those factors.
- ❖ Show some factors that the main parties carry on during the tunnel project.
- ❖ Conclusions and recommendations for such work.

6. Analysis of Collected Data and Discussion

risk matrix beside a colored risk map achieved by means of the Likelihood and impacts results obtained earlier from the questionnaire. Due to such fact that it is far the most simple way to establish what called risk priority table for the risk factors (44) included in the study such a method will provide a clear view for the risk factors that need a certain concern to be managed in order to overcome such issues. Risk matrix priority conducted simply by means of excel tables format to ensure the simplicity and logically format to clear out the risk factors. The questionnaires design based on a pilot study as on recommendation of expert engineers on selected factors and questions. The main layout of questionnaires was conducted in a way to include different sections to simplify the outputs required, those include general information about the respondents, such as experience, age, role in the project, level of educations and so on. Other sections included questions regarding risk management knowledge, risk concepts, evaluation of risk, risk management implementations, risk factors, risk responsibility carrying, and risk management process as a whole (see table 1. For scale used).

Table (1) Scale used in order to identify risk factors likelihood and impact of occurrences

Scale	Like Hood Description	Impact Description
1	Like hood	Very low
2	Rare	Low
3	unlikely	Medium
4	Possible	High
5	Likely	Very high

As showed in (figure 1) the risk matrix map used include four colored zones:

- Green zone: risks in this zone considered low level and accordingly can be ignored.
- Yellow Zone: risks in this zone are of what called moderate importance and eventually should be put into consideration to be under control.
- Orange Zone; risks in this zone are considered critical and have to deal with as soon as possible.

- Red Zone: risks in such zone considered extremely important and dangerous in which it must be put into consideration as a priority to be under serious attention and deal with first (in other words should be avoided if possible).

The questionnaire sent to 37 respondents related to the field of tunnel construction (30 respondents were only eligible within 81% rate) asking for their cooperation to answer depending on their experience and knowledge related to the field of study and to lend hand to prioritize the risk factors included in the study.

Figure 1. Risk Matrix Map after [6]

6.1 Results denoting risk management knowledge

In order to achieve reasonably a reality and dependency on answers gained, the sample respondents selected were (66.67% combined) with experience range 16 years and above in construction field, (Figure2.).

Figure 2. Years of Experience

Questions related to the knowledge of risk and the answers include a (Yes) or (No) as answer were as follows:

- a. Are you familiar with the concept of risk management and the Risk Management Process? Moreover, the answers were as follow
- b. Did you Study or took courses about Risk Management?
- c. The principal of risk management is completely understood in your Company /Organization?
- d. Does the Company/organization have a risk management plan?
- e. Is a risk management process in your Company/organization implemented? Table 2. Illustrate the answers for questions ((a) to (e)).

The majority of answers to (e) were (No) (83.33%) that represent the fact that risk management is actually not implemented from the early beginning of the projects.

f- In Tunnel construction Project which area does risk avoidance/ prevention influence your performance? (Figure 3.)

That specific question (f) gives a clear idea that the main understanding for risk; is that it is mostly related to safety (33.33%) and after that regarding quality (32.14%) with a low level of concerning (time and cost 34.53).

As regarding to section 6.1, the majority of answers were to the side that risk management concept is miss confused with hazards, safety, and low knowledge to the scope of risk management as a whole.

Table 2. answers for questions ((a) to (e))

Questions	Respondent Numbers	(Yes) as Answer	(No) as Answer	(Yes)Percentage %	(No)Percentage %
a	30	15	15	50	50
b	30	6	24	20	80
c	30	6	24	20	80
d	30	6	24	20	80
e	30	5	25	16.67	83.33

Furthermore, As noticed in (a) answers were split (50-50) that would give the first opinion that the related respondents were with a good level of risk management knowledge.

The answers to question (b) were (80%) with (No) as an answer in which it made some kind of a conflict to the first questions related to knowledge of risk management. Which meant that so few of the respondent had a chance to study scientifically about risk management to make clear idea about what is risk and risk management.

Going further to other questions; for (c) risk management is not high and not in the acceptable limit again (80% as No). The majority of answers to question (d) were (80% as No) that was an early indication that management system as a whole in the Company/organization is encountered with a lot of lack.

The majority of answers to (e) were (No) (83.33%) that represent the fact that risk management is actually not implemented from the early beginning of the projects.

f- In Tunnel construction Project which area does risk avoidance/ prevention influence your performance? (Figure 3.)

Figure 3. risk avoidance influencing performance

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6-2 Results denoting importance and implementation of risk management knowledge

The following questions given to the respondents to show whether risk management is actually implemented or not (Yes or No as choices).

a- Does the company/organization use a systemic approach for the identification of risks related to the declared objectives?

b- Was your company/ organization provided by documented risk management plan from the beginning of the pre-study?

c- Was the term “Risk” included in any phase of the project?

d- Do you use any methods to analyze risks? (For example Fault Tree Analysis, Monte-Carlo, What If, etc.)

The answers to such questions illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3 Answers to questions Section 6-3 (a-d)

Questions	Respondent Numbers	(Yes)as Answer	(No) as Answer	(Yes)Percentage %	(No)Percentage %
a	30	4	26	13.33	86.67
b	30	3	27	10	90
c	30	10	20	33.33	67.67
d	30	0	30	0	100

Occasionally as it is obvious, the majority of answers (a) were No (86.67%) this assures lack of knowledge and professionalism in dealing with risk.

Unfortunately for (b), the majority of answers were No (90%) that give a clue that even for different projects there is nothing include documentation of risk management.

The most picked answers for (c) were No (66.67%) here the results were tending to prove the conflict of the term (risk) and what actually it means. As for (d) the answer was shocking because no scientific nor realistic methods used to analyze the risk (100% No). e- What is the level of taking the risk in consideration in the “Early life” of the Tunnel construction project? (give as percentage):

Figure 4 Taking risk level during project phases

As it is noticeable the majority of answers tendency were toward during construction phase (39.7%) which must be put into many exclamations. The misunderstanding to risk and it only deal with safety during the construction phase mostly.

f- Who is responsible for Organizing Risk Management in the company/organization?

Figure 5 who is responsible for risk in the company/ Organization

As noticeable the highest responsibility inside the company/ organization as on Employer (30.49%) and Consultants (25.61%) and with only (2.44%) for risk management as it shows that no such role is available in any governmental organization.

g- Who is responsible for Organizing Risk Management during execution of tunnel project?

Figure 6 who is responsible for risk during execution

Project managers hold the most risk during execution phase with (21.71%) but here they include the role of risk manager (13.95%) but the fact is that no such role is available under that position title.

h- In Which phase of the Tunnel project was the risk management process performed. (risk identification).

Figure 7 Risk Identification

As noticed risk identification is achieved during execution phase, mostly (58.82%) that give the fact that most of the identification is just achieved during the construction phase that is strange because the risk is not shown during the execution only but from the early beginning of planning toward the other phases.

i- In Which phase of the Tunnel project was the risk management process performed. (risk assessment)

Figure 8 Risk Assessment

Again, for (i) the assessment for risks is also mostly made during the execution phase (68.57%) that is not acceptable from managing point of view.

j- In Which phase of the Tunnel project was the risk management process performed. (risk Response)

Figure 9 Risk Response

Again, the response also made mostly during the execution phase (81.82%)

k- Was there an efficient pre-study for the Tunnel project regarding Risk?

Figure 10 was there pre-study for tunnel project regarding risk

The answer was a great concern that No efficient pre-study was implemented regarding risk (76.67%) that percentage seriously dangerous which will lead to a catastrophic end. such as an unfinished project or long time delay and a massive cost overrun.

l- Is availability of Effective risk management will improve the project implementation?

Figure 11 was there pre-study for tunnel project regarding risk

As expected the majority of answers for (l) were YES (100%) a proof that an effective risk management system is not provided in such projects.

As a result, for section 6-2 it was obvious from answers risk management process is not available as it should be or in another word from the beginning to the end of the project. most of risk managing process is done during the execution phase mostly which is a clue that a lack of knowledge is going here.

6.3 Reliability and Validity of data Obtained

Reliability and validity both are the most important and essential lineaments during the evaluation of any measurement for a well research. Reliability

refers to the stability of what was achieved, whereas the validity represents the credibility of findings [Altheide & Johnson, 1994].

For scientific research both considered important concepts in recent researches, as they are used for reinforce the accuracy of the assessment and the evaluation of any research work [Tavakol & Dennick, 2011]. Throughout the study due to statistical purposes, *reliability* and *validity* were established;

Without using and applying reliability and validity of the research, it will be hard to show the errors on theoretical relationships that are being considered for measurement [Forza, 2002].

Cronbach's alpha is one of the most commonly used tools in statistics as measurement for reliability tests. Reliability of any measuring

instrument/questionnaire refers to the extent to which it measures consistently. For this purpose, SPSS software was used to investigate the reliability of the questioners by obtaining Cronbach's alpha. The coefficient of reliability should fall as value in between 0 and 1, with

perfect reliability equaling 1, and no reliability equaling 0. the general rule is that reliability greater than 0.8 are considered as high [Downing, 2004]. In the research the value of the Cronbach's alpha for questionnaires was (0.897) which is considered highly preferable and reliable.

Cases	the Cronbach's alpha	N. of Items
30	0.897	10

6.4 Results Denoting Risk Factors

A number of risk factors were selected (44 factors) according to the respondents and been categorized accordingly and been prioritized according to their degree of risk. Through using equation (1) (5X5) matrix is used afterward a list of top 10 factors will be shown and the whole will be shown in risk map to be noticed through table (4). that the result ranked as follow, starting with the expansion of project time as a first issue with (21.01), war (15.91) and financial (12.85). only top 10 was

shown the others were shown in figure (12) risk matrix map.

For the last column in Table (4) percentage of risk it was calculated based on the fact that maximum risk degree will be (25) so based on this fact dividing the degree of risk for each risk factor by that number will conduct the percentage of risk for example for (C5) $21.02/25=84\%$. Which is a high number that gave the chance that it is high to occur and it is necessarily to be solved or if possible avoided.

Table 4 Risk factors ranked according to risk degree

Risk Factors	Risk Code	Impact	Probability	Degree of Risk	Risk Rank Due to Degree of Risk	Percentage of Risk %
Extending project time	C5	4.57	4.60	21.01	1	84
War & natural hazards	Ex4	4.30	3.70	15.91	2	64
Financial including insufficient funding	O4	4.10	3.13	12.85	3	51
Insufficient estimation for funds	PS1	3.67	2.70	9.90	4	40
Construction cost overruns	C1	3.43	2.73	9.38	5	38
Politics	Ex5	3.43	2.50	8.58	6	34
Design errors and omissions	D1	3.47	2.27	7.86	7	31
Scheduling errors, contractor delays	PM2	3.00	2.20	6.60	8	26
Inexperienced workforce and staff turnover	O1	2.87	2.20	6.31	9	25
Delayed Disputes resolutions	R5	2.73	2.23	6.10	10	24

Table 4 conducted based on the respondents' answers (30 eligible respondents) by using of equation (1) and obtain risk degree which is taken from the averages of impact and probability of respondents answers (Table 5)

$$R = (P * C) \dots 1$$

As for Risk factor, (C5) for example $R = (4.6 * 4.57) = 21.02$

Probability	5	10	15	20	C5
	4	8	Ex4	16	20
	3	PS2,B4,F2,F1,B2,D4	D1	O4	EX4
	2	O2,Ex2,C4,C3,B3,En1,PM1	R5,O1 PM2, F1,B4,F2,D4	C1,F3,Ex5,PS1	10
	1	R1,En2,En3, PL1,C2,B1	PM3,O3,PM5, PL3,D3,PM4,EX 3,F3,D2	4	5
Impact					

Figure 12 Risk map for Risk factors ranked according to risk degree

For figure 12), the all-44 factors were put in the risk matrix, which shows the degree of risk and their zone. As observed, from figure (12) the top 10 factors would vary from dangerous to critical so in that case it must be solved and be paid attention to.

Table (5) Sample of respondents answers

S.N.	Risk Code	Probability weight					Average Probability Weight
		1	2	3	4	5	
		Frequency of occurrences					4.6
1	C5	0	1	1	7	21	30 total

S.N.	Risk Code	Impact weight					Average Impact Weight
		1	2	3	4	5	
		Frequency of occurrences					4.57
1	C5	0	1	3	4	22	30 total

6.5 Results Denoting Responsibility for Risk Factors

Who have the responsibility to manage the following risks in the tunnel project?

As through table 6, it is clear that the most responsible party to hold risk and handle with is in the first place the owner for 6 out of 14 risk events 5 out of 14. Each of the events will normally be chosen according to the events, such as price changes the owner is (37.14%) holding the risk.as for the events related to for example supply of labor the contractor holds (62.5%) if that event had a lack within it.

Table 6 Risks Responsibility

Risk	Owner	Designer	Contractor	Project Manager	Others
Price (changes in the contract amount due to variations in prices and salaries)	37.14	14.29	25.71	5.71	17.14
Delayed payments	39.71	7.35	26.47	7.35	19.12
Changes in design	28.74	29.89	22.99	4.60	13.79
Delays in design	30.43	37.68	11.59	7.25	13.04
Quality of contractual documents	34.67	13.33	24.00	12.00	16.00
Lack of resources during the project execution	34.67	13.33	24.00	12.00	16.00
Supply of labor	2.08	0.00	62.50	16.67	18.75
Collaboration problems	26.19	4.76	28.57	25.00	15.48
Changes in the project conditions	25.96	15.38	23.08	20.19	15.38
Lack of quality in project performance	9.72	2.78	34.72	37.50	15.28
Lack of material quality	7.14	1.43	40.00	37.14	14.29
Lack of materials	7.94	1.59	47.62	26.98	15.87
Capacity and productivity of labor	3.64	0.00	49.09	29.09	18.18
Force majeure risks	35.38	4.62	27.69	6.15	26.15

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

By examining through the obtained results from the analysis of the questionnaire, it was obvious that no effective and realistic system of risk management was applied during any stage of tunnel project. Results range from (66.67 up to 100%) with negative answers (No as an answer). That is mostly due to lack of proper knowledge and experience related to such a field (risk management). Accordingly with through direct interview survey been through it was a misunderstanding to the term risk which was understood as any problem that causes harm (so affecting the safety). Rather, than regarding the fact that risk is any action come through the project phases, which affect the objectives of any project (here regarding time, cost, quality, and safety). so the reality is hard not as what expected if any system of risk were implemented from the early beginning of the project starting with the idea and pre-study through planning, bidding, design, construction, operation, and monitoring. Hence regarding the answers related to section (6-2 h, I and j) demonstrate that the risk actions (identify, assess and response) (58.82%, 68.57%, and 81.82%) were all achieved and applied during the execution phase. The procurement phase was some kind ignored with a max of 5.71% as a percentage that is really strange that means the contractor and contracts are not

responsible and valid as it should be which increases the risk. Regarding the top three risk factors ranked accordingly to their degree of risk those factors gain the top ranks due to the fact that as a result to all previous question no actual risk management process was implemented. No plan for risk and no pre-study or previous documentation found. For infrastructure projects such as tunnels, main road, bridges and so on the process is in need to avoid any catastrophe that will lead to stop, long time delay, massive cost overrun and accidents.

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